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IMPACT OF PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION QUALITY ON PASSENGERS' SATISFACTION IN THE BENIN METROPOLIS, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Public Transportation is essential in urban environment especially in developing countries where many people cannot afford personal transport due to low income. This study was conducted to examine the impact of public transportation quality on passengers' satisfaction in the Benin Metropolis, Nigeria. Five commonly recognized quality indicators of public transportation were selected. These are affordability, accessibility, reliability, frequency and safety/security. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design, using questionnaire to collect data from a sample of 775 public transportation users spread across 25 communities of the study area through randomization. The data were analyzed in the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, while the stated hypotheses were tested using both binary logistic regression and Kendall coefficient of concordance. The result as a whole showed that 65.2% (Cox and Snell R Square) and 92.3% (Nagelkerke R Square) of the variance in public transportation satisfaction was influenced by variation in the selected indicators. It was also shown that four of the five indicators were discovered to make significant impact to the study, but with safety/security and accessibility of public transportation respectively returning the highest positive (88.211) and negative (0.997) influence on passengers' satisfaction. The Kendall coefficient of concordance revealed that there was a significant relationship in the rating of the influence of the selected indicators on public transportation satisfaction. The study concluded that public transportation quality influenced the level of satisfaction in the study area. It is recommended that relevant government agencies and public transportation departments should pay attention to the behaviour of the various public transportation indicators in the study area in order to monitor the quality of public transportation service delivery as well as passengers' satisfaction.*

Keywords: Public transportation; Quality; Passenger; Satisfaction; Benin Metropolis

INTRODUCTION

Public Transportation is an inevitable service in urban environment, and even more inevitable in developing countries due to the low level of income of the majority which cannot afford personal car (Atewe and Ebojoh-Emekpo, 2025). According to Enimola, Makoji and Nafiu (2022), the use of public transportation is subject to economic deficiency of the poor who have no economic willpower to afford personal cars. With the percentage of people living in urban areas

projected to rise above the current half of the world population already in urban areas (Vabuolyte and Uspalyte-Vitkuniene, 2018), it is expected also that the relative proportion of number of poor people in the population would further increase the pressure on public transportation service due to excess demand over supply (Mammo, 2010). This is already manifesting from the crowds of people along major roadsides in many large cities, especially at weekends and festive periods. With more public transportation demand over supply, many public transportation providers

can begin to compromise service quality, which ultimately influence satisfaction for monetary gains.

Presently, there is a broad-range of consensus, not only among the various public transportation providers, but also the travelling public on the important quality indicators for measuring urban public transportation services. In fairness, service quality (SERQUAL) is an abstract word that can be difficult to define, and in many scenarios, may even be confused with satisfaction (Hoyer & Hoyer, 2001; Lien & Yu, 2001). However, the boundary between quality and satisfaction has been established in literature. Oliver (1997, cited in Atewe, 2023) stressed that service quality is more direct and hence, usually refers to cognitive judgments, whereas satisfaction is more encompassing and often used with the affective domain. Placed side-by-side with public transportation, Asogwa (2016) conceived of service quality as “how transit is perceived by users.” This according to Friman, *et al.* (2020) relates to the functionality, information and the comfort attributes of the public transportation system. Therefore, the performance of a public transportation service is measured by its quality attributes, which are the most synthetic and comprehensive indicators (Dragu, Roamn & Roman, 2013). These attributes are perhaps the best and most comprehensive indicators which measure the performance of transportation system (Nevřela, 2008; Raicu, 2007; Tobias *et.al.*, 2009).

Service satisfaction which is a related term to service quality is often influenced by service quality, which in turn determine service patronage (Tuan, *et. al.* 2022). According to Obasanjo and Martina (2015), public transportation satisfaction is the performance of bus services in relation to convenience, safety and transportation fare. Therefore,

satisfaction of customers emerges when the passengers' expectations reaches equilibrium with the actual public transportation service quality for the different public transportation quality indicators (Enimola, Makoji and Nafiu, 2022). Also, the level of satisfaction derived from public transportation service usually follow the extent of adherence to public transportation quality indicators. Hence, the more the adherence to public transportation quality indicator specifications of a city transportation policy, the more enhanced and more likely the satisfaction derived by public transportation users.

Several scholars have attempted to measure public transportation service quality by using different approaches. Deveraj *et al.* (2002), Hartikainen *et al.* (2004) and Lai (2006) have argued that customer satisfaction surveys, mostly carried out using questionnaire, remain generally the commonest instrument for evaluating public transportation quality while employing SERVQUAL indicators of tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy dimensions in gathering relevant information. The SERVQUAL criterion has several parameters for measuring public transportation, and to ascertain the comparable relevance of the various factors affecting passengers' total quality understanding on a five to seven-option Likert log, with the primary reason of separating expectations from observations. This identifies the most salient public transportation service indicators for different economic group and then compares them to the competition in terms of the advantages and disadvantages pertaining to each particular dimension (Parasuraman *et al.*, 1988 cited in Atewe, 2023).

Marsden and Bonsall (2006), Kenworthy (2008), Litman (2008 & 2011), and Tomer, *et al* (2011, cited in Asogwa, 2016) also offered some guidelines for assessing public transport

quality from different perspectives while considering service frequency, availability, fare arrangement and payment categories, convenience and safety, affordability, amenity, information and attraction of services as indicators. Vabuolyte and Uspalyte-Vitkuniene (2018) observed that there were both qualitative and quantitative measurement indicators of public transportation quality. According to them, the qualitative indicators show the benefits to ridership, while the quantitative indicators were more for public transportation operators. The qualitative indicators are: frequency,

regularity of public transportation vehicle, travel time, safety and travel transfer coefficient (Paliulis & Ušpalytė-Vitkūnienė, 2009 cited in Vabuolyte & Uspalyte-Vitkuniene, 2018), while the quantitative indicators include: number of passengers transported, run coefficient, coefficient of passenger-shift, passenger travel time, number of passengers transported per hour and operating speed (Jurkauskas, 2004).

The Quality Approach in Tendering Urban Public Transportation Operation (QUATTRO) project of 1996-1998 developed a quality loop of public transport system (QUATTRO, 1998) (Figure1).

Figure 1: Schematic Quality Loop Model of the Relationship Between Expected and Delivered Level of Public Transportation Service.

Source: Pticina (2011).

Four stages of service dimensions are shown in figure 1: the expected quality which is the minimum quality needed by the people, the perceived quality which is the quality appreciated by public transportation users during their travels, targeted quality is the quality the transportation provider wish to provide for the people, and the delivered quality is the quality which the transportation provider is actually able to offer in real

operating conditions. Hence, target quality may not always be delivered by transportation system in the face of several operational constrains. This leads to the development of satisfaction gap arising from the difference between expectation and observation. In the light of the above, this study attempted to assess the impact of public transportation quality on passengers’ satisfaction in the Benin metropolis using a synthesis of five

major quality indicators by Phoebe (2017), EN 13816 European Standard (2002) and the Statistical office of the European Communities-EUROSTAT. The specific objectives of study were to identify the varying impact of each indicator on public transportation satisfaction and to identify the relationship in the rating of the public transportation quality indicators among users in the study area.

MEASURES OF PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION QUALITY AND SATISFACTION

The EN 13816 European Standard (2002, cited in Pticina, 2011) developed a quality standard-EN 13816 service quality standard for public transportation with reference to QUATTRO. The focus of the study was to promote standard and quality approach to public transportation operations and focusing on customers' needs and expectations. According to the EN 13816 European Standard model, the quality of service is a group of quality indicators with the right set of measures for which the service operator is in charge. Therefore, urban public transportation system quality was defined by eight elements with each element constituting a bundle of indicators. These elements and their indicators include: i. Availability, which indicators are network and time schedule; ii. Accessibility, which indicators were listed to be external and internal interface, and ticketing, iii. Information, with general and travel information as indicators. iv. Time, which has journey, punctuality and reliability as indicators. v. Customer care, with indicators including commitment, customer interface, staff, physical assistance and ticketing options. vii. Security is the seventh element with safety from crime, safety from accident and perception of security constituting the indicators. viii. Environment which is the last

element has pollution, natural resources and infrastructure as its indicators (EN 13816 European Standard (2002) cited in Pticina (2011).

The Statistical office of the European Communities-EUROSTAT identified twenty-one (21) indicators which directly or indirectly characterized urban public transportation service quality. Defining these later indicators along with the components offered by EN-13816 European Standard (2002) model in Pticina (2011), four components of public transportation quality can be observed. These include: i. Availability, which defines the proportion of the area used for land, air and water transportation, length of public transportation network and land area, length of public transportation per inhabitant and number of buses and its equivalents functional in public transportation per 1000 of the population. ii. Accessibility, which is the second component include indicators such as number of parks and ride parking space per 100 of the population, number of parks and ride parking space per 1000 cars, number of stops of public transportation per 1000 of the population, number of stops of public transportation per km², share of the restricted bus lanes from public transportation network, number of stops per 1km of public transportation network, and cost of monthly ticket for public transportation network. iii. Comfort, the third component defines the average age of the buses. iv. Environment the last component encompasses indicators including length of public transportation on fixed infrastructure per 1000 of the population, proportion of public transportation on fixed infrastructure, proportion of public transportation network on flexible routes and length of public transportation network on flexible route per 1000 of the population (EUROSTAT,

Available at: <http://llepp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu>

Obasanjo and Martina (2015) noted that passengers' walking distance from origin or destination to the closest transportation terminal and their waiting time before boarding a vehicle were important criteria for assessing the quality of bus services in any locality. Putting this side-by-side with the report of World Bank (1987), which stated that passengers in adequately served urban areas are supposed to access public transportation terminal within 300-500 meters from their locations to derive the maximum satisfaction from public transportation service. Similarly, the United Nations Human Settlement Programme (2021) recommended a walking distance of 500m or 0.5km for a low-capacity public transportation system and 1000m or 1km for a high-capacity public transportation system for a public transportation to be described as convenience from its access point. Therefore, distances in excess of 500 meters can be tolerated in low density area. Also, World Bank (1987) opined that waiting time that is between 1 and 10 minutes indicate high service quality and maximum customer satisfaction, whereas the maximum period passengers are expected to wait for vehicle arrival at transportation terminals must not exceed 20 minutes, if the transportation quality were to be adjudged high.

De Ona and de Ona (2015) analyzed the quality of public transportation service using customer satisfaction indices. The study summarized the evolvement of research and recent conceptualization as it affects the different methodological approaches for service quality assessment in the public transportation system from the beginning. Kral, Janoskova and Kliestik (2018) report on the work of some researchers in Slovakia on the role of socio-demographic attributes on the

regular patronage of public transportation as indicators of public transportation satisfaction among users revealed that age was among the significant variables that affected the regular use of the suburban bus transport. Rana (2014) in her study of public transportation satisfaction in Amman, Jordan, constructed a user survey to determine the satisfaction of bus, minibus, and jitney users revealed that the bus users were discovered to be the most satisfied. The survey which had two sections: the demographic attributes, and the second part, the travel attributes of the respondents. Using the ANOVA, the results showed that the users of the three public transportation modes disagreed in the following areas: availability of air conditional, availability of the transit service, ease of entering/exiting the vehicle, ease of payment, and staff behaviour.

Study conducted by Rahman, Haque, Ehsan, Rahman and Hadiuzzaman (2017) on passengers understanding of para-transit quality of service in Dhaka City revealed that most people travelled by para-transit service, yet their service was not advanced. Among the major limitations of the informal or Para-transit service highlighted in the study include low standard vehicles, congested seat arrangement, poor noise level, poor movement flexibility and insufficient lighting facilities and ridership safety. Phoebe (2017) investigated the conditions influencing passengers' contentment of Matatus public transportation in the CBD of Nairobi, Kenya. The finding indicated that strong correlation existed between service reliability, affordability, frequency, safety and condition of vehicles and customer satisfaction. Obasanjo and Martina (2015) described service satisfaction in their study of quality of intra-urban passengers' bus service in Kaduna Metropolis as "the performance of bus services in relation to convenience, safety and transport fare". The result showed that the

majority of the respondents were not at peace with the standard of services rendered by buses in the area. Nwaogbe, Ibe and Ukaegbu (2012) study on para-transit service and its operation in Aba town, Nigeria opened some questionable comments on the comfort and safety of service. Although the finding revealed that 77% of its customers were satisfied with the performance of the Para-transit mode of operation in the area, however 92% of the operators complained of poor road network. Therefore, many people choose to patronize public transportation not for their kind of service rendered but due to the absence of a better alternative and the constrained imposed by their income, which scenario may not be different in this present study area.

THE STUDY AREA

The study was conducted in the Benin metropolis, which is an extension of Benin City, the largest city and current capital of Edo State, Nigeria. In terms of absolute location, Benin Metropolis is located between Latitudes $6^{\circ} 11' 29.016''$ N and $6^{\circ} 20' 54.017''$ N of the Equator and between Longitude $5^{\circ} 34' 139''$ E and $5^{\circ} 42' 40.655''$ E of the Greenwich Meridian. The metropolis is a mix of inhabitants of different cultures occasioned by

the activities of migration of people from other parts, although with the indigenous Bini tribe still dominating the population composition. The current status of Benin City as a metropolis was predicated by its expansion over the contiguously built-up space of five Local Government Areas of Egor, Ikpoba-Okha, Oredo, Ovia North-East & Uhunmwode (see Figure 2). This expansion has been continuous along all directions of the city arterials so that settlements which hitherto were not part of the metropolis have now gradually joined. As the arterials get expanded by time and hit up new areas in the sub-urban space, there has been gradual change in the complexity of the socioeconomic activities of the whole metropolis. This changes in turn has resulted in a continuous surge in the traffic interaction between the main urban centre and the sub-urban areas of the metropolis through the arterial corridors at varying degrees (Atewe & Asikhia, 2025). This complexity have also led to public transportation quality gap between the main urban centre and the outer zones of the metropolis (see Vabuolyte & Uspalyte-Vitkuniene, 2018). In terms of population, the city which had over half of the total population of Edo state in the 2006 population census, was projected at 2,173966 for 2023 figures. This speedy rate of population growth underscores the increasing level of public transportation demand especially among the urban poor.

Figure 2: The Study Area Showing the Major Arterial Roads
Source: RECTAS (2013), Modified By Author.

Urban travels in the Benin metropolis generally depended on motorized transportation supplied by both formal and informal arrangements, although with the latter, which were products of different individuals, organizations and corporate bodies dominating the public transportation landscape of the city. The government-owned formal public transportation was limited in supply and had not been expanded along with population expansion, although relatively

organized with marked control in terms of staffing, training and discipline, route of operation and hour of service and amount of fare charged. The individually-owned informal public transportation services which constituted over ninety percent (90%) of public transportation in the study area operated with almost no control in their activities. Apart from licensing, (which was also not receiving full compliance from the operators), enforcing other quality standards

and regulations were observed with many challenges. For instance, the individual owners of the means of transportation determined the amount of fare charged, route and hours of operation and many other operational decisions. As a result, the operators may operate without regards for ethical standard and service quality, to the extent that many vehicles which were not road worthy were observed to operate.

THE RESEARCH METHODS

The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design, as well as the multi-stage sampling technique in arriving at the final respondents for the study data which were collected through a semi-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed for a sample of 775 households drawn from the 2023 total household population (410,807) of the metropolis (Atewe, 2023). This was distributed across twenty-five (25) randomly selected communities of the study area. At the first level of the sampling, five communities were selected each from the five LGAs that made up the metropolis using cluster sampling and thereafter, using randomization. This was followed by a random selection of 31 streets from each of the sampled communities. Finally, a copy of the questionnaire was randomly administered in each street. This was administered to the household heads or their wives in their absence or any other adult individual in the sampled household who had adequate knowledge of the subject matter, and used public transportation as their primary means of transportation for daily interaction.

The data collected were analyzed in the SPSS using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The logistic regression model (see equation 1) and the Kendall coefficient of concordance (equation 2) were respectively used to test the hypotheses: i. public transportation satisfaction is not influenced by

the different quality indicators (affordability, accessibility, frequency, reliability and safety/security), ii. there is no relationship in the rating of the different public transportation indicators by passengers in the study area. In equation 1, P(Y=1) described the probability of a passenger rating the overall service as being satisfactory, while [1-P(Y=1)] represented the probability of a passenger rating the overall service as not being satisfactory, given the satisfaction level of the individual service components as determined by the different quality indicators. This probability fell between 0 and 1 (0≤J≤1) for all the possible independent variables.

$$\text{Logit}(y) = \frac{P(Y=1)}{1-P(Y=1)} a + X, \dots\dots\dots\text{Equation 1,}$$

Also, α and β represented the intercept and the vector of slope coefficients respectively while X was the vector of the explanatory variables representing the satisfaction level for individual service components as determined by their quality indicators. The parameters in the model was estimated using maximum likelihood estimation method. In operationalizing the model, public transportation service satisfaction was the predicted variable (Y), while the predictor variables (X₁, X₂, X₃, X₄ and X₅) include the different explanatory variable of the public transportation indicators. In another level, defining the parameters of the Kendall coefficient of concordance (equation 2), SS represented the sum of squares of the deviations of each R_j from the mean, ‘n’ was the ‘number of items being ranked, while ‘k’ was equal ‘t’ the number of raters.

$$W = \frac{SS}{(n3 - n)k2/12} \dots\dots\dots\text{Equation 2}$$

This combination of model parameters were used to examine the relationship and agreement in the performance rating of the selected public transportation quality

indicators by individual passengers of public transportation service in the study area. Public transportation quality was measured by the level of aggregate satisfaction passengers derived from the service. This was done by measuring the individual quality indicator selected: affordability, accessibility, frequency, reliability and safety/security of vehicles. Affordability was measured by the average amount in Naira (₦) spent on public transportation. Accessibility was measured by the average walking distance from the nearest boarding point to residence or place of work. Frequency was measured by the number of trips covered by public transportation operators per day. Reliability which Tyrinopoulos and Antoniou (2008) referred to as the consistency of public transportation's punctuality and on-time performance of scheduled was calculated by the average waiting time of passengers before boarding a public transportation. Also, safety or security was calculated by estimated proportion of public transportation vehicles that were not road worthy in relation to those that were road worthy.

In measuring the selected indicators on public transportation satisfaction, for the public transportation system to be described as accessible, the study adopted the UN-Habitat (2021) average walking distance of 500m from place of work or residence to the nearest public transportation terminal for areas with low capacity of public transportation system and 1km for areas with high capacity of public transportation system. Also, for the service to be considered as reliable, the World Bank (1987, cited in Atewe, 2023) maximum waiting time allowance of 20minutes was adopted. To measure affordability of the public transportation in the study area, Olvera *et al.* (2008) 15% of monthly income expenditure on public transportation benchmark was adopted. In this case, the

percentage of the personal income of passengers were used (see Statistics South Africa, 2013). Therefore, monthly/annual expenditure on public transportation for personal income above 15% was considered a breach of affordability. Safety/security of the public transportation system was determined using the physical attributes of the sampled public transportation vehicles. The selected attributes include availability of both side mirrors, availability of seat belts (most especially for drivers), adherence to the city red-yellow colour commercial code, possession of driver's licence, optimal public transportation route and the relative proportion of old vehicles/cleanliness of vehicles. These attributes were carefully selected and identified by the researcher and his assistants during the field survey. Finally, frequency of the public transportation system was determined using the number of trips covered by a public transportation operator. This was used as an indirect measure of the relative speed of public transportation vehicle en route, level of road congestion and the characteristics of the road infrastructure. Along this direction the higher the number of trips by public transportation vehicle, the higher the level of satisfaction derived by passengers, as long as the speed standards of public transportation were not violated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DEMOGRAPHIC AND SOCIOECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE STUDY POPULATION

The demographic and socioeconomic attributes of the study population considered are represented in Table 1. Of particular attention of these demographics is the income distribution of the population, which revealed that most of the people were low-income earners. This can only suggest that majority of

them might not have a personal car because of their small size of income, and therefore might have to depend on public transportation for their mobility needs. In this regard, any compromise in the quality of public transportation provision would have serious

negative impact on the people, especially the urban poor whom the society was supposed to protect because of their economic fragility (Atewe & Ebojoh-Emekpo, 2025). Therefore, where the expected public transportation quality is not always delivered, this tends to create a satisfaction gap for passenger

Table 1: Demographic and Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>
Male	347	44.8	44.8
Female	428	55.2	100.0
Total	775	100.0	100.0
<i>Age Group</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>
< 20	0	00.0	00.0
21 -40	283	36.5	36.5
41 -60	484	62.5	99.0
Above 60	8	1.0	100.0
Total	775	100.0	100.0
<i>Education</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>
No Formal Education	35	4.5	4.5
Primary Education	170	21.9	26.6
Secondary Education	315	40.6	67.0
Tertiary Education	255	32.9	99.9
Total	775	100.0	100.0
<i>Occupation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>
Formal Sector (Public and Private)	167	21.5	21.5
Trading/Business	298	38.5	60.0
Artisanal	229	29.5	89.6
Farming	34	4.4	94.0
Others	47	6.0	100.0
Total	775	100.0	100.0
<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>
Single	80	10.3	10.3
Married	656	84.6	94.9
Divorced	3	0.4	95.3
Widow/Widower	36	4.6	99.9
Total	775	100.0	100.0
<i>Income Level of Respondents</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Cumulative Percentage</i>
≤₦30,000.00	73	9.4	9.4
₦30,001.00 – ₦74,000.00	562	72.5	81.9
₦74,001.00 – ₦118,000.00	113	14.6	96.5
₦118,001.00 – ₦162,000.00	23	3.0	99.5
₦162,001.00 – ₦206,000.00	1	0.1	99.6
≥₦206,001.00	3	0.4	100.0
Total	775	100.0	100.0

Source: Author’s Field Survey.

IMPACT OF PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION QUALITY ON PASSENGERS' SATISFACTION

Table 2 showed the descriptive statistics of the logistic regression analysis. The result revealed that 69.0% of the total sample

represented the positive outcome, while 31.0% of the responses stood for the negative outcome. The information in the table (Table 2) further showed that all cases selected were included in the model, and that there were no missing or excluded values.

Table 2: Case Processing Summary and Dependent Variable Encoding

<i>Case Processing Summary</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>Frequency (N)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Selected	-	775	100.0
Missing Cases	-	0	00.0
<i>Variable Encoding</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>Frequency (N)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Not Satisfied With PT	0	240	31.0
Satisfied With PT	1	535	69.0

Footnote: PT = Public Transportation

Source: Author's Field Survey.

Meanwhile, the pseudo-R-squared measures of the logistic regression model in Table 3, revealed that 65.2% (Cox and Snell R Square) and 92.3% (Nagelkerke R Square) of the variance in the dependent variables (public transportation satisfaction) were the result of variation in the explanatory variables. Consequently, the high value of the Nagelkerke R Square (Table 3) which is supposed to adjust the Cox and Snell to reach

a maximum of 1, indicated a good relationship between the associated explanatory and the explained variables as well as how well the model fitted the data. This therefore explained how well the explanatory variables selected collectively improve the likelihood of varying the explained variable which represented the level of public transportation satisfaction by passengers.

Table 3: Binary Logistic Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	132.185 ^a	.652	.923

Estimation terminated at iteration number 9 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001.

Source: Author's Field Survey.

From the result, four out of the five selected indicators were discovered to make significant contribution to the model. These are affordability, accessibility, frequency and

safety or security of vehicles, but with safety or security being the strongest predictor of public transportation satisfaction with an odd ratio of 88.211 (Table 4). This implies that, at

every unit increase in the number of qualities of sound or road worthy vehicles, the level of satisfaction with the public transportation service would increase by an odds ratio of 88.211 when compared against unsound or not road worthy vehicles. This suggests that safety or security indicator was seriously impacting public transportation satisfaction in the Benin metropolis and thus was a major considerations of public transportation patronage in the study area. In connection, the finding agreed with the works of Abenzoza, et al (2017) and Ha, et al (2019) which discovered that users' perception of public transportation safety was one of the major variables influencing passengers' travel satisfaction and loyalty. Therefore, passengers would normally prioritize feeling safe or secured from accidents and other associated dangers with public transportation whenever they wish to travel. This study also discovered that frequency of public transportation had a significant positive impact on public transportation satisfaction with an odd ratio of 1.26 controlling for other factors. This suggests that, a unit increase in the number of hours an operator stayed on the road, the level of satisfaction with public transportation service was likely to increase by a positive odds ratio of 1.26. Very intriguing, however, the affordability indicator of public transportation quality satisfaction returned a 'no association' (1.0) odds ratio between quality and the level of satisfaction. This means that the relationship between the variables was neither negatively nor positively influenced. The implication here is that, any unit change (upward or downward) in public transportation fare was not necessarily influencing the level of satisfaction of users in the study area. This may be due to a lack of direct alternative to public transportation service among users. On the other hand, accessibility to public transportation terminal which was determined by distance walked

from the nearest boarding point to residence or place of work had a significant negative odds ratio of 0.99. This indicates that any unit increase in distance to public transportation terminal, the level of satisfaction by public transportation users would decrease by an odds ratio of 0.99, thus suggesting that distance between individual location and point of accessing public transportation facility was greatly influencing the level of satisfaction derived from the service.

Without gainsaying, distance barrier is a major influence of public transportation accessibility and satisfaction. Therefore, passengers should not exert too much time, energy or resources just because they want to access a public transportation terminal. According to World Bank (1987), passengers in adequately served urban areas, are supposed to access transportation terminal within 300-500 meters from their locations. Also, the UN-Habitat (2021) recognized a walking distance of 500m (1/2km) for a low-capacity public transportation system and 1000m (1km) for a high-capacity public transportation system if a public transportation is to be considered as convenience from its access point. Therefore, distance in excess of 500 meters or 1/2km can be tolerated in low density area. Reliability was another indicator that returned a significant negative odds ratio (Table 4). For every unit increased in the waiting time of public transportation, the level of satisfaction would decrease by an odds ratio of 0.72 while holding other factors constant. This indicates that waiting time, which was the measure of reliability in the study had an inverse relationship with public transportation satisfaction. Therefore, the longer the waiting time before passengers' board a public transportation, the lower the level of satisfaction derived from the service. This observation agreed with the work of Obasanjo and Martina (2015), which noted that

passengers’ waiting time before boarding a vehicle were important criteria for assessing the quality of bus services in any locality. As a result, the UN-Habitat (2021) suggested that the maximum time passengers are expected to wait for vehicle arrival at transportation terminals should not exceed 20 minutes if the transportation system were to be adjudged high in terms of quality and satisfactory. According to Chakrabarti and Giuliano (2015), to ensure the reliability of public transportation system, policymakers should make sure that public transportation vehicles consistently operates according to its scheduled departures and arrivals so as to reduce the length of waiting time.

Judging from the results, it was observed that, the five explanatory variables have accounted for individual level of public transportation satisfaction at different proportion. However, safety and frequency of public transportation vehicles appeared to influence passengers’ level of satisfaction more. We also observed that, while increased in waiting time (reliability) and distance to public transportation terminal (accessibility) were negatively impacting on passengers’ satisfaction, an increased in operator’s time/hours on the road (frequency) and number of sound vehicles in relation to unsound vehicles (safety) on the other hand were positively impacting the level of public transportation satisfaction in the study area (Table 4).

Table 4: Variables in the Logistic Regression Model Equation

Variables	B	S.E.	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I.for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Average Cost of Fare (Affordability)	.000	.000	14.427	1	.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Waiting Time (Reliability)	-.317	.050	39.539	1	.000	.729	.660	.804
Distance to PT Terminal (Accessibility)	-.003	.000	33.830	1	.000	.997	.996	.998
Number of Day Trips Per PT Vehicle (Frequency)	.237	.150	2.499	1	.114	1.267	.945	1.699
Worthiness of PT Vehicle (Safety & Security)	4.480	.684	42.944	1	.000	88.211	23.102	336.825
Constant	4.497	1.553	8.382	1	.004	89.773		

a. Variable (s) entered on step 1: Average fare, waiting time before accessing public transportation, proximity to public transportation terminal, operator time on the road, worthiness of public transportation vehicle.

Source: Author’s Field Survey.

The study further showed that the average cost of fare (affordability), which was the fifth independent variable, returned a significant ‘no relationship’ positive odd ratio of 1.000. This means that, any unit increased in public transportation fare did not necessarily influence the level of satisfaction in the negative direction. Rather, passengers were still prepared to accept the service especially against the backdrop of non-availability of

state provision of public transportation in many areas of the metropolis as well as the inability to afford personal car and ride-hailing services by majority of the people. This scenario looked much like extortion and rub of standard and yet not noticed because of absence of true alternative among the people especially the urban poor. Overall, the beta values of the result (see Table 4) helped to explain the level of the impact of each

indicator on the level of satisfaction by public transportation users. Hence, the study showed that safety/security, accessibility and reliability of public transportation vehicles had strong impact on public transportation satisfaction in the study area with respective odd ratio of 88.211, 0.99 and 0.72. However, while safety/security returned a positive impact on public transportation satisfaction, accessibility and reliability on the other hand returned a negative impact. This dynamism of responses to the different indicators by public transportation users is important for guiding service improvement and analyzing the perception of public transportation and satisfaction of different social and demographic groups.

In another level, the result of the Kendall coefficient of concordance in Table 5 helped to reveal the level of agreement among the transportation users in the ranking of the different selected quality indicators (accessibility, reliability, frequency, affordability and safety of vehicle) of public transportation in the study area. Along this direction, the finding showed that most of the respondents ranked safety as the most satisfied indicator, while frequency was ranked as the least satisfied indicator. Also, the test result showed that there was a significant relationship among their preferences, an indication that there were agreements among the individual ranking of public transportation quality indicators (Table 5).

Table 5: Ranking and Individual Preference of Public Transportation Quality Indicators

Public Transportation Quality Satisfaction Indicator	N	Mean Ranks	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Kendall Coefficient of Concordance	Test Statistics
Accessibility	775	3.50	.862	1	5	N	775
Reliability	775	2.27	1.002	1	5	Kendall's W ^a	.578
Affordability	775	2.91	1.177	1	5	Chi-Square	1791.559
Frequency	775	4.73	.704	1	5	Df	4
Safety and Security	775	1.58	.773	1	5	Asymp. Sig.	.001

Source: Author's Field Survey.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, it was observed that the selected indicators exert different dimension of influence on the outcome variable, satisfaction. Overall, the study revealed that the applied logistic regression model strongly fitted the data, judging by the return of high Cox and Snell and Nagelkerke R-squared values that were both closer to 1. The study further revealed that four out of the five indicators were significantly influencing the level of passengers' satisfaction of public transportation. These are affordability, accessibility, frequency and safety/security of

vehicles, but with the strongest positive and negative influence on passengers' satisfaction associated with safety/security and accessibility to and from place of residence/place of work to public transportation terminal respectively.

Very intriguing, however, the study found that affordability, which measured the average amount returned a 'no association' odd ration of 1.000. This meant that there was no association between the explanatory variable (affordability) and the odd of the outcome (satisfaction) occurring. While increase in the waiting time (reliability) and distance to public transportation terminal (accessibility)

negatively impact on passengers' satisfaction, an increase in the number of trips by public transportation operators per day (frequency) and number of sound vehicles in relation to unsound vehicles (safety) on the other hand positively impacted the level of passengers' satisfaction in the study area.

The outcome of the Kendall coefficient of concordance revealed that there was a significant relationship in the respondents' rating of the influence of the selected quality indicators on public transportation satisfaction in the study area. The findings presupposed that policy initiative towards public transportation provision and improvement should take into account the beta value presented by each of the selected indicator as manifested in the model equation. Therefore, the higher beta value for a positive attributes or indicators as shown from the measure of road worthiness of vehicles (safety or security) indicated a strong positive impact on the outcome variable, transportation satisfaction. Similarly, the higher beta value for a negative attribute or indicator as evidence from the result of distance evaluation of public transportation terminal (accessibility) and waiting time before boarding public transportation service (reliability) by passengers indicated a strong negative impact on satisfaction. The study therefore brought to bear the relationship

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between public transportation quality and passengers' satisfaction. The study therefore recommended that relevant government agencies as well as public transportation departments should take special attention of the major indicators of public transportation quality and satisfaction in the study area. To achieve this, government policy should be targeted towards enhancing public transportation standard through regulation for improved quality of service delivery. Also, transportation experts and researchers as well as published transportation articles should be consulted for adequate policy direction that would ensure improved public transportation system for users' satisfaction.

ENDNOTES

The author was in the defunct Department of Geography and Regional Planning, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City as at the time of the study.

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